

Effect of Financial Knowledge on the Performance of Small and Medium Enterprises in Gombe State

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Abstract

The need to examine financial knowledge for the improvement of performance of SMEs in Gombe state necessitates this study. The main objective of this study is to examine the effect of financial knowledge on the performance of registered SMEs in Gombe State. The independent variable (IV) is financial knowledge measured by debt management and saving while the dependent variable (DV) is SMES performance. This study employed quantitative design. The population of this study was 779 registered SMEs with Gombe State Ministry of Trade, Industry and Tourism. Data for the study were collected through the use of five point likert-scale questionnaire from 264 respondents who are the sample size and were randomly selected through the use of simple random sampling method. Data was analyzed through the use of SPSS for descriptive analysis and partial least square method Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) version 4.1.8 for hypothesis testing. The findings reveal that, financial knowledge has a significant positively affects on SMEs performance. The study concludes that financial knowledge has positive and significant effects on the performance of SMEs in Gombe state and lack of financial knowledge is the major problem faced by many SMEs. Therefore, based on the above findings, the study recommends that; Government and relevant stakeholders should develop and implement comprehensive financial literacy and financial support programs tailored for SMEs owners and managers to improve their knowledge on financial concepts. Moreover, this study contributes to the literature on financial knowledge concept and the performance of SMEs and it will serves as a guide to policy makers and reference material for other researchers.

Keywords: Financial Knowledge, debt management, saving and SMEs performance.

1. INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background to the Study

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) is a vital driver of world economic growth as it is propelled by a strong entrepreneurial base and activities that promote productivity levels, employment generation capacity, achieving sustainability among most nations of the world and the benefit MSMEs provide for economic growth have long been recognized and are well documented (Yeboah, 2021). Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) is the backbone of the economies since the industrial revolutions in Europe and United States of America (USA) (Zonouzi *et al.*, 2020).

Small Enterprises are those enterprises with 10 to 49 employees and with capital base of 5million to less than 50 million excluding land and building, while Medium Enterprises are those enterprises with 50 to 199 employees and with capital base of 50 million to less than 500 million excluding land and building (National Policy on MSMEs 2020). Small and medium enterprises have now become one of the main stakes of achieving development in most of the countries in the world. Similarly, SMEs generate employment, value added and contribute to the gross domestic product (GDP) of a country and are considered the engines of economic growth in developing countries (Ratanova: & Voroncuka, 2021) and also supported that SMEs are generating approximately 60 percent of employment as the key drivers of employment growth.

On a global scale, research shows that of most existing businesses, approximately 90% are represented by SMEs, creating over 50% of the world's employment (World Bank 2019). SMEs are all over not only in a single country. Consequently, SMEs account for 99.9% of the UK's private sector businesses of the business population of 5.6 million businesses and offered over 60% of the private sector employment in the UK (FSB, 2019). Similarly, South Africa Statistics of 2023 shows that, of all formal businesses in South Africa, SMEs account for most businesses, contributing 34% to the country's gross domestic product (GDP) while employing between 50% and 60% of the country's population (Mashele, 2023). SMEs contribute significantly to the GDP of the world's significant economies. Moreover, In Nigeria, entrepreneurial activities in the small and medium enterprise (SME) accounts for 46.54% of the country's GDP (Olaore *et al.*, 2021). MSMEs in Nigeria account for 96% of the total number of businesses in the country and contribute about 50% to the national GDP (PwC'S MSME Survey 2020). However, performances of SMEs in Nigeria have failed to produce the desire expectation and higher economy development despite all these contributions.

Currently, In Nigeria SMEs performance has reduced drastically, the persistence reduction of the performance results in closing down of much business, lying off most workers, unemployment, insurgency and economy degeneration (Effiom *et al.*, 2022). This indicates the presence of low profits, low market share, low sales, and absence of growth expansion among others. Moreover, Manufacturers Association of Nigeria (MAN) (2024), state that, over a hundred businesses, including SMEs, multinationals, closed operations last year, with the latest being Procter and Gamble, who shut down on-ground operations and switched to an import-only in December 2023. Furthermore, the low performances of SMEs call for interventions, measures has been taken by Government in promoting SMEs through the provision of support that helps in accelerating SMEs performance. Moreover, Ibrahim & Bardai, (2021), posits that, the Government support SMEs through Small and Medium Development Agency of Nigeria (SMEDAN) established through the SMIDA Act 2003 among others.

Nevertheless, this study observed that performance of SMEs is relatively low in Gombe state living many SMEs owners/managers with no or little goods in the enterprises despite all these supports; some are even place out of the business. SMEs are managed by owners/managers who operate day to day activities of the enterprise. Generally, managers are decision makers and play a key role in the decision-making process, organizing, motivating, controlling and setting objectives related to the acquisition, allocation, and utilization of economic resources (Herrity 2024). Managers help in moving organization forward towards achieving its objectives.

In order to act effectively for better performance, it is assumed that every SMEs manager/owner must be financially literate; this implies having financial knowledge that is the ability to read, analyze, manage and write about the financial conditions of the firm (Joseph, 2021). Financial knowledge (FK) is an essential component of everyone's daily reality. Moreover, financial knowledge is the level of knowledge or understanding that individuals have of their personal financial concepts or principles, which individuals need as the basis for making decisions on effective financial management, as well as a key factor in financial literacy (Adiputra *et al.*, 2021). Financial knowledge plays a very important role in the growth of SMEs, its ability of individuals to manage their finances starting from planning, budgeting, managing, spending, checking, controlling, keeping proper records and delivering daily funds for living needs. In addition, the role of FK to SMEs growth can never be over emphasis, It enables manager to have the knowledge of critical financial concepts, for instance, types of interests, risks, returns of investments, diversification of investments, among others (Susan, 2020; Trianto *et.al.*, 2021). For example, performance includes business efficiency, growth rate, profitability, liquidity, market share, expansion, (Glosenber *et al.*, 2022).

Therefore, this study aims to contribute to the existing literature by providing a comprehensive examination of the effect of financial Knowledge on the performance of SMEs in Gombe State to closed the gaps which were not recognized by the pervious researchers in the state through debt management and saving.

1.2 Statement of problem

The significance of SMEs can be appreciated from the perspective of the promotion of growth; innovation and prosperity of developed and developing economies, also enabling environment, and good infrastructure contribute significantly to the development of SMEs (La porta *et al.* 2020). Similarly, SMEs oath to have good performance, good performance is a crucial indicator of SMEs success this was supported by Yeh *et al.*, (2020); Huang *et al.*, (2022), for example, it includes business efficiency, growth rate, profitability, liquidity, market share, expansion, (Glosenber *et al.*, 2022), and staff growth rate (Welsh *et al.*, 2023).

Currently, this is a mirage, Performance of SMEs in the globe have failed to produce the desired and expected impact on the growth of SMEs and the development of the entire economy, the world has been characterized by the occurrences of SMEs failure, organizations failure, and among others (Heredia *et al.* 2022). Furthermore, Kalemli-Özcan, *et al.* (2020) reported a sharp increase in the global SMEs difficulties such as poor funding, high cost of logistics, insufficient technology, lack of skill and the failure rate was also from 4.5% to 12.1 % in 2020.

Moreover, Bartik *et al.*, (2020) and Foos, (2020) conducted a survey in March, 2020 and find out that 43% of out of 6000 small businesses had low performance, some have temporarily closed, large reductions in employees and the majority of SMEs have less than 1 month of cash on hand which attributed to the lack of funds, poor management.

Similarly, United state statistics shows that in 2020, places like Colorado, Florida, Nevada, and New York have highest proportion of failed small businesses with 13.5% failure rate which resulted in laying off of many workers, closing down of many SMEs and reducing the development of the nation (Georgieva, 2024). Moreover, Africa has the highest entrepreneur rate in the world according to a Nigeria MSME report but approximately 80% of micro, small, and medium-sized businesses throughout Africa fails within their first half-decade due to low performance as a result of insufficient capital, infrastructure and lack of knowledge (Gbemi, 2022)). In addition, the failure rate also reaching between 70 and 80% in South Africa (Bushe, 2019). It means that most African MSMEs are experiencing difficult situation which leads to low performance.

Currently, In Nigeria SMEs performance has reduced drastically due to array of challenges confronting business operators in various area of the country. Among which include; cost of acquiring and maintaining electronic payment devices, Lack of adequate infrastructure, lack of finance and a poor business environment (Ali *et al.* 2020). Moreover, Low level of FK such as recordkeeping attitudes, poor cash management, management accounting among others is still identified as barriers to SMEs maintaining their performance (Safitri, 2021); (Wardani & Darmawan 2020) and Gusaptono (2020).

Persistently, many SMEs continue to closed in Nigeria due to poor performance, at least 1.9 million SMEs have been lost since 2017 to 2023; business closures persist at a high rate, (Timi 2023). For instance, Pivo banking service, lazerpay company, bundle Africa crypto, payday fintech company and zazuu also afintech company were all short down in 2023 (Samson, 2023). Gombe state is not in exception, there are allots of SMEs that close down from 2019 to date such as Gombe Dadaka floor mill, Proper pure water enterprise, Batore tyre marchants, leschin global venture, Aliku provision and beverage venture among others, that this study observed. However, SMEs low performance may be due to lack of financial knowledge especially in Gombe State. In addition, since there is not even one study on financial knowlege on the performance of SMEs that was carried out in Gombe State as of the time of this study; this may be the reason why SMEs continue to shot down or experiencing much failures as well as low performance in Gombe State. In view of this, this study wants to close the existing gaps that emanate.

On this note, performance was measured by market share, profitability, growth and expansion, this study believes that financial knowledge with its indicator (debt management & saving) may help in addressing SMEs problems through proper transferring of financial skills and all the necessary knowledge needed by SMEs actors that will promote performance of enterprises. Moreover, this study examines the effect of financial knowledge on performance of registered SMEs in Gombe state.

In line with the above problems statements, the following research questions were raised to guide the study:

- i. What is the effect of debt management on the performance of SMEs in Gombe State?
- ii. What is the effect of saving on the performance of SMEs in Gombe State?

1.3. Objectives of the study

The aim of this study is to examine the effect of financial knowledge on the performance of SMEs in Gombe State. The specific objectives are:

- i. To investigate the effect of debt management on the performance of SMEs in Gombe state.
- ii. To examine the effect of saving on the performance of SMEs in Gombe state.

1.4. Research Hypotheses

H₀₁; Debt management has no significant effect on the performance of SMEs in Gombe State.

H₀₂; Saving has no significant effect on the performance SMEs in Gombe State.

CHAPTER TWO

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Introduction

This chapter reviews the effect of financial knowledge on Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) performance. It includes conceptual, empirical and the theoretical reviews.

2.2 Conceptual Review

This sub-chapter discusses the concepts of SMEs, financial knowledge, debt management, saving, and also explains the conceptual model of the study.

2.2.1 Small and Medium Enterprises

In 2019, world bank defined SMEs as an enterprise that play a crucial role in global economy by Contributing significantly to employment, job creation, income generation, economic competitiveness and overall social development. SMEs account for the majority of businesses worldwide and are important contributors to job creation and global economic development, they represent about 90% of businesses and more than 50% of employment worldwide (World Bank 2019). Similarly, European Union defined enterprises as medium enterprises with fewer than 250 employees, an annual turnover that does not exceed 50 million euros, and/or an annual balance sheet total not more than 43 million euros. An enterprise is defined as a small enterprise that has fewer than 50 employees, an annual turnover total that is not more than 10 million euros, and/or an annual balance sheet total that does not exceed 10 million euros. (European Union commission 2003).

In Nigeria, the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) has, through its various circulars and intervention fund programmes of August 2017, generally defined Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) as entities with asset base of N5 million and not more than N500 million excluding land and buildings with employees between 11 and 200. Small Enterprises are those enterprises with 10 to 49 employees and with capital base of 5 million to less than 50 million excluding land and building, while Medium Enterprises are those enterprises with 50 to 199 employees and with capital base of 50 million to less than 500 million excluding land and building (PwC'S MSME Survey 2020).

2.2.2 Performance

Bire *et al.* (2019) defined SMEs performance as the work results achieved by individuals; adapting to the individual's role or duties in a company in a certain period, which is linked to a certain value measure or standard of the company the individual works in or an achievement of success or failure of organizational goals that have been implemented. The word Performance is derived from the Latin word "Performare" which means to accomplish an activity that has been ordered. Performance current meaning originated from English word "Perform" which means to implement something that requires certain ability or skill (Amos *et al.*, 2023). Business goal achievement measured against standards, completeness, and costs. (Desiyanti & Kassim, 2020). Business performance represents how well the company can make use of business assets and generate receivable.

According to Dura *et al.* (2022), financial performance is an analysis carried out to see the extent to which a company has implemented financial rules properly and correctly. Company performance is a description of the financial condition of a company which is analyzed using financial analysis tools so that to know about the good and bad financial condition of a company which reflects work performance in a certain period.

Consequently, Amos *et al.*; (2023), posits that, performance is measured in terms of market share, profitability, growth and Business expansion. Similarly, Santoso *et al.* (2022) looked at performance from the perspective of innovative and financial achievement. So, firm's performance can be viewed in different dimensions such as number of employees, customer satisfaction, product and process innovation among others. In this study, performance was measured from the following perspective:

Profitability: Profitability here means the measure of efficiency and it is defined as the business's ability to produce a return on an investment based on its resources in comparison with an alternative investment (Anderson & Trujillo, 2022). Profitability simply means the ability of business to earn profit. Profit is equal to total revenue left after minus total cost, including other expenses. Profitability is the company's ability to generate a profit during certain period (Miswanto *et al.*, 2022). So, profit is the pillar of every business.

Growth: According to Francis-Smyth and Robertson (2021), growth is good objective for business due to the fact that it measures business success and it is a key driver to wealth creation, Economic development and employment opportunities in most countries of the world. The combination of firm's specific resources, capabilities and routines resulted into growth.

Business Expansion: This expansion could be in form of increase in marketing, adding sales employees, adding franchisees, opening of another location, forming an alliance, offering new products or services, entering into new markets, merging with or acquiring another business. Lucas (2021) explains that business expansion is a growth strategy achieved by increasing the number of physical locations where customers can buy products and services.

Market Share: Market Share represents the percentage of an industry, or markets total sales, that are earned by a company over a specific period of time. this is use to give a general idea of the size of a company in relation to its market and competitors (Hayes *et al.*, 2021). Market Share increase can help a company to achieve greater scale, improves operations and profitability.

2.2.3 Financial Knowledge

Financial knowledge (FK) is an essential component of everyone's daily reality. Financial knowledge is the level of knowledge or understanding that individuals have of their personal financial concepts or principles, which individuals need as the basis for making decisions on effective financial management, as well as a key factor in financial literacy (Adiputra *et al.*, 2021). A good financial foundation of the owners of SMEs is significant measure of success. This refers to one's basic financial knowledge such as risk diversification, skills, numerical ability, and foresight including their use in overcoming financial problems. Moreover, Knowledge refers to what individuals know about personal financial matters, as measured by their level of knowledge about various personal financial concepts (Atlas, 2019). Financial knowledge is the understanding of someone who considers the concept of finance to be very important, such as budgeting and record keeping.

Similarly, Rai *et al.* (2019) posits that financial knowledge is an important factor in promoting SMEs and also in making one's financial decisions which may include financial planning, saving, account management among others. According to Wulandari *et al.* (2023), financial knowledge is very influential on everyone's financial management behavior because financial knowledge has a function to determine the direction or basis for making good financial decisions leading to excellent performance of SMEs. Indicators in Financial Knowledge include 4 concepts, knowledge of personal financial management, knowledge of money and asset management, knowledge of credit and debt, and knowledge of savings and investments (Wulandari *et al.*, 2023). Thus, the above studies mean that, good financial knowledge has a positive effect on SMEs performance.

According to Kumari and Harikrishnan (2021), SMEs must have financial knowledge in order to manage their finances well and healthily so that long-term business sustainability can be felt and can reduce the impact of conditions such as during the last pandemic. Furthermore, the components of financial knowledge which are proxies that measure it in this study are debt management and saving.

2.2.4 Debt management

According to Jennifer calonia, (2023), debt management is a way to get your debt under control through financial planning and budgeting, the goal of a debt management plan is to use these strategies to help SMEs lower their current debt and move toward eliminating it. Similarly, Andira *et al.* (2024) explained that debt management is the process of establishing and executing a strategy for managing business debt to raise the required amount of funding, pursue its cost/risk objectives, and meet business goals of SMEs such as developing and maintaining an efficient and solid market for the products.

Additionally, Tsenov (2020) posits public debt management is the process of covering the government's spending needs, and also to achieve goals and meet the regulatory requirement of the national and the Community law. Furthermore, Ebuka *et al.* (2022) assert that debt management is the gamut of institutional arrangement in organizing the liabilities of a country so that the debt service burden is kept within sustainable level. Nigeria's debt, like that of most other African countries appears to be on a ceaseless and perpetual increase. This was supported by Zainal *et al.* (2020) in contrast, if the reimbursement rate is poor, it will damage both the borrower and microenterprises. In this instance, the borrowers cannot receive the next larger loan and the borrower loses its customer because there is not proper loan repayment (Thabiso & Smangele, 2022). So, if the SMEs actors cannot manage debt appropriately, there will be loss of confidence which will negatively affect the performance of the firm. Lack of this knowledge can hamper the growth of SMEs.

2.2.5 Saving

According to Julia (2023) Savings refers to the money that a person has left over after they subtract out their consumer spending from their disposable income over a given time period and it's representing a net surplus of funds for an individual or household after all expenses and obligations have been paid. Similarly, Savings habit is a crucial need for individuals / business actors to obtain and practice in order to solve their future spending decisions (Saber, 2022). Saving is a particularly critical issue for owners of micro and small enterprises that have minimal access to credit. A strong foundation in saving literacy can significantly enhance micro entrepreneurs' capacity to manage debts effectively and knowing also about savings mechanisms and planning for future financial needs, entrepreneurs are better equipped to allocate resources (Carlos, Mejía, Gutierrez, & Rodríguez, 2023). Nevertheless, the individual management of their money will influence the sustainability and performance of these micro and small enterprises. Maata *et al.* (2020). Savings significantly encourage investment and boost economic growth and are significant to be used during emergencies, saving literacy is a challenge for some individuals, particularly those in SMEs despite having a high net income; many microenterprises' owners struggle to set aside money for savings or investment purposes Tarisha *et al.* (2021). Furthermore, the extremely low level of personal savings paired with the high levels of personal debt among individuals and SMEs raises concerns because personal savings are the main source of finance entrepreneurs use to launch and expand their businesses (Bernard, 2020). SMEs are constantly faced with the dilemma of whether to save the money or spend all the money on goods, saving behavior is a critical requirement for SMEs actors to help them figure out

how to solve potential future financial decisions themselves by learning and rehearsing good financial skills in their business to improve performance (Maata *et al*2020). Saving is very important to every SMEs owners/manager for survival of the firm.

2.2.6 Conceptual Model

A conceptual framework illustrates the expected relationship between variables. The aim of this study is to examine the effect of financial knowledge on the performance of SMEs in Gombe State. In this study, the Independent Variable (IV) is financial knowledge while the Dependent Variable (DV): is performance of SMEs However, the proxies used for measuring financial knowledge are debt management and saving as shown in figure 1 below.

Figure 2.1

Conceptual Model

Independent Variable

Dependent Variable

Sources: Adapted from Yakob *et al.* (2021).

2.3 Empirical Review

This sub-section reviews previous related research works done by other researchers related to the work.

2.3.1 Debt management and SMEs Performance

Zainal *et al.* (2022) studied the Role of knowledge transfer in determining debt literacy towards micro enterprises 'ability to repay debt in Malaysia. The aim of this study is to investigate the relationship between debt literacy and the role of knowledge transfer in impacting the ability of micro enterprises to repay its debt in Malaysia. The population of the study was 903, 174 micro enterprises service subsector institution establishments in Malaysia (SME Corp. Malaysia, 2020). Data for the study were collected through closed-ended questionnaires from the sample size 127 which was selected through the use of simple random sampling method which resulted in a response rate of 33.07 percent of Malaysian micro enterprises. The PLS-SEM approach was employed to evaluate and analyzed the data and subsequently to solve hypotheses and achieve the research goals. The findings reveal that, knowledge transfer is positively significant to micro enterprises ability to repay debt with a beta value of 0.736, t-value of 17.364, and p-value 0.000, where p-value < 0.05. The study suggest that government agencies should recognized micro enterprises in Malaysia due to their knowledge, awareness, practices, management, and capability which is particularly significant for the government also.

However, the sample size of the above study was one hundred and twenty seven (127) which is relatively small, compared to the present study. So, the findings of the study cannot be generalized.

Thabiso and Smangele (2022) Studied financial literacy and SMEs loan repayments in South Africa during the COVID-19 era. The aim of the study was to investigate the relationship between financial literacy and loan repayment of SMEs. The study followed a positivist paradigm, and a quantitative approach was employed. A total of 110 self-completed Likert questionnaires were distributed to shop owners in South Africa, only 107 were filled correctly and analyzed using SPSS. The results from Pearson's correlation coefficient showed a strong and significant relationship between financial

literacy and SME loan repayments at $r = 0.324$, $P < 0.0005$. Regression analysis showed a significant linear relationship between financial literacy and SME loans repayments. The results imply indicated a positive relationship between debt management and SMEs performance. Therefore, the study concluded by suggesting that SME owners need business financing coaching in accessing credit, and negotiate for better loan agreements, which may include interest rate diminution and repayment period, among other things.

However, the study analyzed data using SPSS with small sample size of 110 which is relatively small to compare 264 sample sizes used by this study and the present study used both smart PLS-SEM and SPSS for data analysis.

Arinda (2019) studied financial literacy and financial performance of small and medium sized enterprises. The aim of the study was to analyze the effect of debt management literacy on the financial performance, to assess the effect of book keeping literacy on the financial performance of small and medium enterprises in Ntungamo Municipality Uganda. The study deployed across-sectional survey design where a sample of 97 SMEs was selected using stratified random sampling technique. Responses were collected using a self-administered questionnaire that was comprised of Likert scaled questions. Data collected was analyzed using SPSS version 23.0 where regression analysis was performed to establish the effect between the variables. The study established that debt management literacy (Adjusted $R^2=0.077$, P -value = 0.015) significantly and statistically affect and predict financial performance of SMEs. However, the study under review was conducted in Uganda which is a different geographical location compare with the present study which was carried in Gombe state Nigeria.

Andira *et al.* (2024); studied the influence of debt policy, dividend policy and profitability on the value of Manufacturing Companies in Indonesia. The aim of the study was to examine the debt policy, dividend policy, and profitability of Indonesian Stock Exchange-listed manufacturing companies from 2018 to 2022. The data was analyzed using multiple regression analysis. The result shows that debt management does not increase performance of the company. Based on the data analysis carried out, it is concluded that debt management (DER) does not have a positive or significant influence on manufacturing company value.

However, the study under review used secondary data with a small sample size of 32 companies. This present study used primary data with a sample size of 264, so the findings of the review study cannot generalize because the sample is too small to be accepted.

2.3.2 Debt Saving and SMEs Performance

Zainal *et al* (2024) studied Microenterprises' ability to repay debt. Do saving literacy and knowledge transfer matter? The aim of the study is examined the factors affecting the ability of Malaysian micro-enterprises to repay their debts, including financial management. The study employed quantitative design and data was collected from the 127 micro-enterprises in Klang Valley. The study used PLS-SEM technique to analyze the data from the respondents and test hypotheses to achieve research objectives. The results show that, saving literacy impact micro-enterprises' ability to repay their debts. The study concludes that, micro- enterprises needs to improve their saving habits to enable them improve their performance.

However the study under review was carried out abroad, that is a different geographical area entirely to compare with the present study which was carried out here in Gombe State, Nigeria.

Ayub *et al;* (2020) conducted study on the role of business grant assistance, micro saving and financial knowledge towards Bumiputera SMEs business performance in Sabah Malasia. The study aimed to examine the influence of business grant, micro saving, and financial knowledge towards Bumiputera SME business performance in Sabah. The study adopted quantitative research design and primary data was collected from the 96 respondents who return their questioners out of 187 questioners distributed. The data was analyzed using SPSS version 26 and Smart PLS 3.0. The study confirms significant positive relationships between micro saving towards Bumiputera SME performance in Sabah and the study concluded that Government should consider the need for business support to Bumiputera SME in Sabah.

However, the above study used a sample size of 96 SMEs which is relatively small compared to this study that uses a sample of 264 SMEs.

La Rocca, *et al;* (2019) studied Cash holdings and SME performance in Europe: the role of firm-specific and macroeconomic moderators. The aim of the study was to examine the ways in which cash holdings affect firm operating performance in a wide sample of European small and medium-sized enterprises. The study used descriptive design and Orbis Europe database version 129 was used for the analysis of secondary data taking from companies with the financial data during the period from 2008 to 2015 in 36 European countries. The findings of the results show that, cash holdings have a positive effect on operating performance, supporting the relevance of precautionary savings motive for SMEs. The study concluded that, SMEs should form habits of saving because Cash holdings, is importance for transaction and savings motive, are positively related to firm performance.

The above study was on cash holdings and SME performance in Europe while the present study is on financial literacy on the performance of SMEs in Gombe State.

2.4 Theoretical Review

This study will review two theories namely: Financial specialization theory and Resource base view theory and association between financial knowledge, financial behavior and financial attitude for small and medium enterprises is underpinned by financial specialization theory.

2.4.1 Financial Socialization Theory

The Financial Socialization Theory was first proposing by Gudmunson and Danes (2011). The theories propose a conceptual model that integrates family socialization theory and recent trends in FL research, aiming to understand individual differences in FL from a socialization perspective. The theory broader conceptualization of FL suggests it is a continuum of abilities influenced by demographic factors (such as age, gender, income, marital status) and socioeconomic factors (education, culture, language, and residence). Financial socialization refers to the process by which individuals not only acquire theoretical knowledge of finance matters but also learn attitudes and behaviors affecting their financial behavior. Financial behavior is “a pattern of action over time such as earning, saving, spending, and gifting” and also includes “decision making” (Gudmunson and Danes, 2011).

Financial attitudes, knowledge, and capabilities are directly associated with financial behavior. Financial behavior then is directly associated with financial wellbeing, as are financial attitudes, knowledge, and capabilities. It was also supported by Ullah, & Yusheng (2020) that, financial socialization that takes places through formal sources, such as schools, and informal sources, such as family and peer groups. The cardinal objective of SMEs actors is to achieve greater performance and SMEs actors who possess adequate financial information literacy are able to increase and sustain their firms’ performance (Gudmunson and Danes, 2011). Financial specialization theory helps in creating more awareness of financial information that may help the individual/SMEs actors to experience financial well-being.

2.4.2 Dual process theory

The foundations of dual process theory are probably ancient. Spinoza (1632) and James (1842) were the first founders of this theory (Baghaei & Ghaffarzadagan 2016). Spinoza, distinguished between the passions and reason and James believed that there were two different kinds of thinking: associative and true reasoning. The theorist theorized that, empirical thought was used for things like art and design work. James (1842) posits that, images and thoughts would come to mind of past experiences, providing ideas of comparison or abstractions, for the success of any investment, the usage of past experience is very necessary. Associative knowledge was only from past experiences describing it as only reproductive and also that true reasoning could enable overcoming “unprecedented situations” that may hinder SMEs success just as a map could enable navigating past obstacles.

The Dual Process Financial literacy theory argues that the behavior of people with a high level of financial literacy might depend on the prevalence of the two thinking styles: Intuition (system 1) and cognition (system 2). It was also supported by Glaser and Walther, (2013) that, Intuition is the ability to acquire knowledge without inference or the use of reason and Cognition is the mental processing that includes the comprehending, calculating, reasoning, problem solving and decision making. Intuition provides views, understandings, judgments, or beliefs that cannot be empirically verified or rationally justified.

Similarly, the theory was recently used by Bellini-leite (2022) whom affirms that Dual Process Theory is currently a popular theory for explaining why individuals show bounded rationality in reasoning and decision-making tasks.

Therefore, SMEs actors who have financially literate can out performed those with low financial literacy as the result of the knowledge that is embedded on them such as record keeping skill, account management, saving knowledge, financial planning among others.

3.1 Methodology

The objective of this study was to investigate the effect of financial knowledge on SMEs performance. This study employed quantitative design. The population of this study was 779 registered SMEs with Gombe State Ministry of Trade, Industry and Tourism. Data for the study were collected through the use of questionnaire from 264 respondents who are the sample size and were randomly selected through the use of simple random sampling method. The questionnaire consisted of structured research questions with a modified Likert-type ranging from the scale of 5 (1 = strongly disagree, 2=disagree, 3 = moderately agree, 4- agree, and 5 = strongly agree). Data was analyzed through the use of SPSS for descriptive analysis and partial least square method Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) version 4.1.8 for hypothesis testing, it was employed because it has the capacity to test the interrelationship between constructs, and to test theoretical model that best fit the data at hand. The findings reveal that, financial knowledge has a significant positively affects on SMEs performance.

4.1 Analysis of Data

This section presents the results of the analysis conducted on the data collected from the respondent. The descriptive statistics, correlation, regression, and t-test results are presented in the subsequent subsections.

Table 4.1 Descriptive Statistics of Variables

Constructs	N	Min	Max	Mean	Std. Deviation
Debt management	264	1	5	4.12	.921
Saving	264	1	5	3.85	.896
Small and Medium Enterprises Performance	264	1	5	2.28	104

Source: (SPSS V23 Output, 2025)

Table 4.1 presents the descriptive statistics of the variables of the study. They are debt management and saving on SMEs performance in Gombe State. All the variables of the study are measured on a five-point Likert scale. Table 4.1 shows a mean response of 4.12 on debt management, having a standard deviation of .921. This means that, all the mean response of the respondents were 4.12 which is the recommended threshold for strongly agree (SA), thus, it shows that majority of the respondents Strongly agreed that debt management positive effect on their SMEs performance in Gombe state.

Similarly, saving also shows mean response of 3.85 which falls within the threshold for agree (A), with a standard deviation coefficient of .896, shows that respondents agreed to statements on saving to positively improve performance.

4.3 Convergent Validity of the Model

The convergent validity assesses how correlated items of a latent constructs are with others while discriminant validity measures how uncorrelated items of one latent construct are with items of other latent construct. To discover the convergent validity of the model, the researcher checked the following against the established thresholds: constructs factor loadings; Average Variance Extraction (AVE), Cronbach's Alpha (CA) and Composite Reliability (CR) not to be less than 0.6.

Table 4.2 Construct Reliability and Validity

Construct	Items	Loadings	AVE	CR	CA
SP	SP2	0.874	0.809	0.921	0.944
	SP3	0.906			
	SP4	0.899			
	SP5	0.920			
	DM	DT1			
DT2	0.784				
DT3	0.941				
DT5	0.899				
SV	SV1	0.720	0.684	0.903	0.927
	SV2	0.855			
FK	SV5	0.930			

Source: PLS-SEM V 4.1.8, 2025

Note: AVE represents Average Variance Extracted; CR represents Composite Reliability; CA represents Cronbach's Alpha. Base on the table 4.6 above, the value of the Cronbach's Alpha and Composite Reliability (CR) for the SMEs performance (SP) construct is 0.921 and 0.944, for debt management (DM) latent construct is 0.915 and 0.935, Saving (SV) latent construct is 0.903 and 0.927.

4.4 Discriminant validity of the model

Table 4.3 *Discriminant Validity using Heterotrait-monotrait ratio*

To authenticate the model used, this study also uses Heterotrait-monotrait ratio being one of the new method to assess discriminant validity.

Constructs	Heterotrait-monotrait ratio (HTMT)
DM<-> SV	0.884
SA<-> DM	0.875
SP<-> DM	0.803
SP <-> SV	0.826

Source: PLS-SEM V.4.1 Discriminant Validity (2025)

Table 4.3 shows that, the HTMT ratios for assessing discriminant validity among indicators were found to be good and below 0.9 at a significant level of p-value less than 0.05 when using the technique in Kock (2024). To establish discriminant validity, the value of HTMT should be lower than 0.9 (Franke & Sartedst 2019).

Discriminant validity is an indication of the extent at which a construct is differentiated from other constructs in a study.

5.4 Value of Endogenous variable

This subsection presents the value of endogenous variable (SMEs performance) in Gombe state.

Table 4.4 Adjusted R-square

	R-square	R-square adjusted
SMEs Performance	0.189	0.177

Source: PLS-SEM V.4.1.8 (2025)

The above table shows, Inner Model Evaluation R-Square: The value of R-square (R²) is zero to one. If the R-Square (R²) value is getting closer to one, the independent variables provide all the information needed to predict endogenous variations.

4.6 Effect Size of Exogenous Variables

This subsection presents the effect size of the exogenous variables on the endogenous variable in Gombe state.

Table 4.5 *Effect Size*

Constructs	f^2	Effect Size
Debt management	0.013	Small
Saving	0.047	Moderate

Source: PLS-SEM V.4.1 effect size, 2025

Table 4.5 shows the effect size of debt management and saving (Exogenous variables) on the SMEs Performance (Endogenous variables) in Gombe state Nigeria. Debt management has small effect 0.013 (13%) on the SMEs Performance while saving has moderate effect 0.047 (47%) respectively.

4.7: Predictive Relevance of Exogenous Variables

The study employs the Stone-Geisser's Q^2 value to assess the predictive relevance of the exogenous variables. The result is presented in Table 4.5

Table 4.6 *Predictive Relevance*

Construct	SSO	SSE	$Q^2 = 1 - SSE/SSO$
EP	0.6790	0.5720	0.420

Source: PLS-SEM V.4.1 prediction Summary, 2025

Note: SSO represents Sum of squared of observed omitted values; SSE represents Sum of Squared Error. Table 4.6 presents the result of cross-validated redundancy of the relationship between debt management and saving on the SMEs Performance. Q^2 is 0.420 which is greater than zero which shows the predictive relevance of the direct path model. The model has high degree of predictive relevance on SMEs Performance. (Gorondutse, & Hilman, 2019).

4.8. Bootstrapping Analysis

A bootstrapping analysis was carried out to determine the direct effect of the exogenous variables on the endogenous variable of the study. The study carried out bootstrapping analysis using 264 cases.

4.8.1: Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis testing is carried out through the bootstrapping method by making a decision to accept the hypothesis based on the significance value (P Value) and the T-table value. The study tested for the effect of financial knowledge (FK); debt management (DM) and saving (SV) on SMEs performance (SP) in Gombe State. Table 4.6 presents the result of the test of hypotheses.

Table 4.7 Path Coefficient

Paths	Beta Value	Mean	Standard dev.	T statistics	P values	Decisions
HO ₁ : DM-> SP	0.302	0.312	0.108	2.805	0.005	Rejected
HO ₂ : SV->SP	1.282	1.308	0.366	3.508	0.000	Rejected

Source: PLS-SEM Path Coefficient, 2025

*** p< 0.01; **p< 0.05; *p <0.1

Table 4.7. Shows the path relationships between the exogenous and the endogenous variables. It shows that hypothesis HO₁ which states that debt management has no significant effect on the performance of SMEs in Gombe State was rejected; which means that, debt management has a positive significant relationship with SMEs performance in Gombe state. The relationship was statistically significant at *P value of 0.005* which is lower than the threshold of *0.05* and the alternative hypothesis was accepted.

Similarly, saving has a positive relationship with SMEs performance of selected SMEs in Gombe state. The relationship was statistically significant at *P value of 0.000*, this means that saving has significant effect on performance of selected SMEs in Gombe state, the HO₂ was rejected.

4.9 Discussions of Findings

This study provides two (2) key findings for SMES owners/managers, researchers, stake holders and governments; the results posit empirical evidence that financial knowledge have positive effects on SMEs performance in Gombe State. The findings are consistent with majority of the previous studies empirically reviewed.

4.9.1 Debt management and Performance of SMEs

The study finds a positive significance effect of debt management on performance of SMEs in Gombe State, with a statistically significant path coefficient ($p = 0.005$). The implication of this significant positive effect is that, higher debt management literacy levels among SMEs owners and managers in Gombe State better the business performance outcomes. This indicates that improving financial knowledge and skills of small business leaders can enhance profitability, productivity and growth of their enterprises. This finding is in line with the findings of Zainal *et al.* (2022); Arinda (2019) and Andira *et al.* (2024) these studies show that with adequate knowledge of debt management, business decisions can lead to the development of the capabilities required for surviving a crisis and ultimately making a business success.

4.9.2 Saving and Performance of SMEs

This research identifies a positive significant influence of saving on the performance of SMEs in Gombe State, evidenced by a significant path coefficient ($p = 0.000$). This substantial beneficial impact implies that Gombe State's SMEs' owners and managers that possess good saving literacy will performance better. This finding is in line with the findings Zainal *et al.* (2024); Ayub *et al.*; (2020) and La Rocca, *et al.*; (2019) this finding show that with adequate knowledge of saving, business decisions can lead to the development of the capabilities required for surviving a crisis and ultimately making a business success.

5. Conclusion

In conclusion, this study affirms that financial knowledge is a vital determinant of the performance of SMEs in Gombe State. The results indicate that enhancing financial knowledge among SMEs owners and managers can lead to improved business outcomes in Gombe State. As SMEs are crucial for economic development, particularly in developing regions, investing in financial literacy programs can yield significant benefits not only for the enterprises themselves but also for the broader economy.

5.1 Recommendations

SMEs owners and manager with sound financial knowledge, will automatically outsmart those with lower or no financial literacy. In view of the findings that emerged from this study and the conclusion drawn, the study makes the following recommendations:

1. The findings show that financial knowledge has a positive significant effect on SMEs performance in Gombe State. Therefore, government and relevant stakeholders should develop and implement comprehensive financial knowledge programs tailored for SME owners and managers.
2. Policymakers should improve more in making a policy that will incorporate financial knowledge into the curriculum of business education at various levels to ensure that both present and future entrepreneurs are equipped with essential financial skills (debt management and saving skills) that can help enhancing SMEs performance.

5.2 Suggestions for Further Study

1. The current study adopts SEM-PLS, for analysis to examine the effects of financial literacy on performance of SMEs in Gombe state. The study uses two independent variables. The coefficient of determination, R^2 , was 1.77 (18%) which explained the effects of the four independent variables. This means that the two constructs used explains 18% of the variance in SMEs performance while 82% is not yet determined. Therefore, there is need for subsequent studies to examine the effects of other financial knowledge indicators that will make up the remaining 82% such as financial innovation, budgeting, investment and management accounting.

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